

Perforce Installation Guide (v0.4)

by Qiang Wei

This document provides a simple instruction on how to install perforce in Windows-based PC. There is also an FAQ in the LERSSE Portal: https://lersse.ece.ubc.ca/tiki-view_faq.php?faqId=4 (login first)

1. Download the perforce client installation file from the download page <http://www.perforce.com/perforce/downloads/ntx86.html> by selecting “**Core Perforce Windows Installer**”
2. Execute the file.
3. Select “User Installation”

4. Select all. It will consume 18M of your disk space.

5. Select a destination directory.

6. Configure the client. It is the most important step in the installation. Set the server port as **lersse-p4.ece.ubc.ca:1666** and set the username as your **ECE account**. Use the default for the other two.

7. Click Install and start the installation

8. Click Finish

9. Start your P4V program

10. In the “Open Connection” dialog, type your password first. As this document will become public, I am not going to put the password here. Please get your password from me personally. After typing the password, click “new...” besides “open workspace (optional)” to create a new workspace.

11. Name your new workspace. The name should follow this convention: youraccount-yourcomputername.

12. Configure your new workspace. Make sure that “Owner” is your account, and “Host” is your computer name, and “Root” is a directory in your PC where you store your project files, e.g. “d:\depot” and the first part of “View” is “//depot/...” (In this way, you can I can browse all the files in the depot). Click “Save”.

Owner:	qiangw
Host:	qiangwei
Description:	Created by qiangw.
Root:	d:\depot
AltRoots:	
Options:	<input type="checkbox"/> allwrite <input type="checkbox"/> clobber <input type="checkbox"/> compress <input type="checkbox"/> locked <input type="checkbox"/> modtime <input type="checkbox"/> mdir
LineEnd:	local
View:	//depot/... //qiangw-qiangwei/...

13. Click ok. Make sure that workspace is your newly created space.

14. Done. You will see that you have successfully logged in. Notice that you need to create the directory structure in your local workspace first. For example, **//Root/projects/active/your_project_name** and store some dummy file there. Only after you submit some dummy files, you can see your project directory structure created in the depot. An alternative way is that I, as a “super user”, can create the directory structure for you first, so that you can just update your local directory with the depot directory. Let me know if you need help on this.

15. For further information on how to use P4V, please read this document.
<http://www.perforce.com/perforce/doc.051/manuals/p4v-gs/p4v-gs.pdf>

Some Guidelines:

1. **//depot/lersse/references/references.bib should be used for ALL publications** produced at LERSSE unless a publication is coauthored with an external collaborators, who already have their own Bib files. Remember to read the instructions (`//depot/lersse/references/compile_it_to_test_references.tex`) on modifying `//depot/lersse/references/references.bib` file.
2. **Please use the following naming convention for all the files and directories** in Perforce, unless there is a very good reason to use other convention (e.g., correlation between Java class to file names):
 - a. all names are low case
 - b. no spaces are in the names
 - c. use underscore ("_") between full words in the namesrationale: 1) file systems on different OSs have different sensitivity to character case and 2) it's inconvenient to use files with spaces in their names when working at the command prompt.

Some Tips:

3. If you encounter problem using P4V to change your password, please consider using P4web. "I couldn't change/set my password through P4 application, so I ended up running the P4web service and then use my browser to access the user settings and modify from there. This is useful for people who wants to change their password. Without a password, I wasn't able to access files in the depot (P4 did not log me in because I didn't have a password - probably treated me as a guest)"
4. "An easier way to set the "view" of the new workspace is to click the "view" tab and navigate to the folder that you are interested in and right click on it and choose "include tree". then you can go back to the "form" tab and edit the stuff."